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Exploring Phytoremediation Potential of *Lantana camara* L. for Heavy Metal Pollution

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Abstract- Industrial effluents and mining activities pose a widespread concern globally. Traditional methodology for cleaning contaminated soils have been used for a long time. Therefore, natural metal hyper accumulator plants species are important for removal of heavy metals. *Lantana camara* L. is a widespread weed and popular ornamental plant of family of Verbenaceae. It is found throughout various regions of India and is extensively used in traditional medicine for various ailments. An attempt to investigate the environmental impact of heavy metal pollution on *Lantana camara* L. was carried out to find out their heavy metal accumulation capability and phytoremediation potential. Concentration of different heavy metals such as Iron, Zinc, Manganese, Nickle, Led, Chromium and Cadmium were analysed in aerial parts viz., shoots, leaves, flowers and fruits and they were in different ranges. This approach has shown promise in remediation efforts, particularly for areas contaminated with heavy metals and by determining the heavy metals in various plant parts suggested that this plant can be used as a hyper accumulator and potential phytoremediation agent.

Key words: *Lantana camara* L., Heavy metal, Pollution, Hyper accumulator, Phytoremediation.

INTRODUCTION

Soil is a crucial environment where rock, air, and water coexist at their interface. Soil pollution can be defined as the prolonged presence of radioactive materials, toxic compounds such as heavy metals, salts, and chemicals, or disease-causing agents that have detrimental effects on plant and animal health. This pollution primarily leads to the deterioration of soil quality, texture, and its mineral and chemical content, ultimately disrupting the biological balance of the ecosystem.

Soil contamination with heavy metals is a significant global crisis due to their varied toxicity, persistence, bioaccumulation, and bio magnification throughout the food chain.¹ This contamination adversely affects soil health

on a large scale, impairing vital ecosystem services. Heavy metals are particularly harmful due to their non-biodegradable nature, long biological half-lives, and potential to accumulate in various body parts. Their solubility in water makes them extremely toxic even at low concentrations, posing severe health risks to humans and animals due to the difficulty of elimination from the body. Nowadays, heavy metals are widespread because of their extensive use in industrial applications. Wastewater often contains substantial amounts of these toxic metals, leading to significant environmental problems.^{2,3}

Excessive accumulation of heavy metals in agricultural soils through wastewater irrigation can lead to soil contamination and affect food quality and safety.⁴ Soils polluted with heavy elements such as chromium, arsenic, lead, cadmium, copper, zinc, mercury, and nickel assess a

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significant risk to resources of groundwater through heavy elements filtering.^{5,6}

Phytoremediation refers to the mechanisms by which higher plants mitigate the chemical impacts of the soil they grow in. Essentially, it is an environmentally friendly, technique to accumulate heavy metals in plant tissues, allowing for the recycling of contaminated soils. The term “phytoremediation” originates from the Greek word “Phyto,” meaning plant, and the Latin word “remedium,” meaning cleaning or rehabilitation.⁷ This method is low-cost, safety and practical, particularly for managing soil in developing countries.⁸ The plant species used for phytoremediation belong to several families, including Asteraceae, Brassicaceae, Fabaceae, Poaceae, Euphorbiaceae, Verbenaceae, and Violaceae.⁹

Plants have a selective potential to accumulate heavy metals through phytoremediation.¹⁰ When these phyto remediator plants enter the food chain, they can impair consumer health.¹¹⁻¹⁴ These plants can grow in contaminated soils because they have developed mechanisms to minimize the effects of heavy metal exposure.¹⁵

Phyto-remediator plants are categorized as hyper accumulators, excluders, or indicators based on their strategy for surviving in metalliferous soils.^{16, 15} Excluder species restrict the translocation of heavy metals from their roots to above-ground tissues, maintaining low concentrations of these metals in their shoots across a wide range of soils.^{15, 17}

Many research studies have been conducted and published on the phytoremediation potential of certain plant species for the removal of heavy metals from contaminated soils.^{16, 18-25} However, limited studies have assessed the phytoremediation potential of *Lantana camara* L. Therefore, the overall purpose of this study to assess the potential of selected plant species for heavy metal accumulation at Dahej industrial estate area (SEZ, GIDC) of Dahej, Bharuch, Gujarat, India by determining the concentration of heavy metals of various plant organs of selected plant species.

MATERIALS & METHODS

Plant materials:

Various parts of *Lantana camara* L. were collected from the Dahej industrial estate area (SEZ, GIDC) of Dahej, Bharuch, Gujarat, India.

Fig. 1- *Lantana camara* L.

Methods

The shoots, Leaves, Flowers and Fruits of selected plant organs were sun dried for a week. Ground to fine powder and stored in packed jar to protect from humidity and light. This powder was used for extraction and estimation of heavy metals. For extraction of selected metals, dry ash of plant samples was prepared. The contents of crucibles were cooled to room temperature in desiccators and 10 ml of 20% HCl was added, the mixture was heated to dissolve its content. Further it was run on Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometer under standard conditions for quantitative determination of Fe, Zn, Mn, Ni, Pb, Cr and Cd.

Statistical Analysis:

All the experiments were repeated thrice, and replicates were maintained for each experiment. The values are given as mean and standard error (SE). All the means were analyzed using one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA, $\alpha = 0.05$) followed by Tukey's test using Graph Pad Prism 6.01.

RESULTS

Shoot

Heavy metals accumulation in shoot of *Lantana camara* L. was found in different levels. Maximum accumulation has been detected for Fe (46.91 ± 0.45 mg/kg) followed by Mn (30.17 ± 0.09 mg/kg), Zn (17.86 ± 0.19 mg/kg), Pb (17.47 ± 0.15 mg/kg), Ni (4.85 ± 0.10 mg/kg), Cr (3.26 ± 0.01 mg/kg) and Cd (1.76 ± 0.20 mg/kg).

Leaves

This study shows that the accumulation of different heavy metals is higher in the leaves than the shoot of *Lantana camara* L. The highest accumulation of Fe (66.91 ± 0.45 mg/kg) and lowest accumulation of Cd (20.76 ± 0.20 mg/kg) was found in the leaves. In the case of other metals, they were found in the ranges of Mn (50.23 ± 0.09 mg/kg), Zn (37.86 ± 0.19 mg/kg), Pb

(37.47±0.15 mg/kg), Ni (24.85±0.10 mg/kg) and Cr (23.26±0.01 mg/kg).

Flowers

Lantana camara L. flowers showed higher content of Zn (46.53±0.11 mg/kg), Mn (53.15±0.11 mg/kg) and Ni (25.76±0.09 mg/kg) with compared to leaves & fruits. Whereas leaves showed higher content of Fe (61.01±0.24 mg/kg) and Pb (33.46±0.05 mg/kg) compared to flowers & fruits. The proportion of Cr (23.21±0.12 mg/kg) and Cd (21.12±0.08 mg/kg) in the flowers was nearly similar in the leaves but slightly lower to fruits.

Fruits

In the fruits, the accumulation of Fe (52.03±0.12mg/kg) was higher and Cd (19.5±0.13 mg/kg) was lower than the other metals. Other metals were found in between ranges of Fe and Cd were Mn (37.37±0.04 mg/kg), Zn (35.78±0.23 mg/kg), Pb (26.23±0.10 mg/kg), Ni (22.10±0.12 mg/kg), Cr (20.99±0.12 mg/kg).

Fig. 2- Accumulation of different heavy metals in *Lantana camara* L. shoot. Each bar shows the mean values (n = 3) and error bar as standard error. Bars having same letters are not significantly different (p ≤ 0.05) according to Tukey's test.

Fig. 3- Accumulation of different heavy metals in *Lantana camara* L. leaves. Each bar shows the mean values (n = 5) and error bar as standard error. Bars having same letters are not significantly different (p d” 0.05) according to Tukey's test.

Fig. 4- Accumulation of different heavy metals in *Lantana camara* L. flowers. Each bar shows the mean values (n = 5) and error bar as standard error. Bars having same letters are not significantly different (p d” 0.05) according to Tukey's test.

Fig. 5- Accumulation of different heavy metals in *Lantana camara* L. fruits. Each bar shows the mean values (n = 5) and error bar as standard error. Bars having same letters are not significantly different (p d” 0.05) according to Tukey's test.

DISCUSSION

The normal heavy metal contents of terrestrial plants growing in uncontaminated soils were found to be in range of 50 mg/kg for Pb, 0.5-2 mg/kg for Cr, 0.01-1 mg/kg for Cd, and 1-5 mg/kg for Ni. The present study showed that concentrations of Cr, Pb, Cd and Ni metal studied in the *Lantana camara* L. growing in Dahej industrial estate area were higher than the plant growing in normal soil. Thereby these plants have a strong ability to tolerate and accumulate these heavy metals. It is also found that, leaves, flowers and fruits of *Lantana camara* L. accumulated more metals concentration then shoot. Similar type of investigation by using four heavy metals Cr, Pb, Cd and Ni was also carried out in *Lantana camara* L. by Wao *et al.* (2014)²⁶ and reported that the concentration of these heavy metals was higher in the plant growing industrially polluted area in Bhopal.

The normal range of heavy metals for Fe, Mn and Zn are 10.0 mg/kg. In this study the range of heavy metals concentration is comparatively also higher for these metals in *Lantana camara* L. Kahangwa *et al.* (2021)²⁷ suggested that there is a higher accumulation of heavy metals in organs of *Melinis repens*, *Lantana camara*, *Leucaena leucocephala* and *Blepharis Maderaspatensis*. They suggested that these plant species can act as hyper accumulator.

Phytoremediation mechanism of *Lantana camara* L. for the various metals like Hg, Ni, Pb, Cd, Cu, Cr, Fe and Zn were also evaluated by Panhekar *et al.* (2015)²⁸, Fang *et al.* (2014)²⁹, Pandey *et al.* (2015)³⁰, Pandey & Bhattacharya (2018)³¹.

CONCLUSION

Now a day, heavy metal in the soil is a serious problem and a danger to both the human health and environment. Long-term exposure to contaminated environments can cause several health problems, including dizziness and cancer. Phytoremediation is an emerging technology of implementing green plants to reduce the toxic effect of heavy metals in the environment, which is cost-effective and an alternative to the conventional remediation approaches. Phyto-remediator plants have been categorized as hyper accumulators, excluders or indicators according to their strategy for surviving metalliferous soil. This study was conducted to assess the potential of phytoremediation technology, focusing on the efficacy of *Lantana camara* L. plant. Results revealed that the heavy metals concentrations in the investigated plant species exceeded normal values, indicating higher accumulation, particularly in plant like *Lantana camara* L. in the area under study. The results also showed that the accumulation of heavy metals in medicinal plants depends upon the climate of locality, air pollution, soil contamination and other environmental factors where the plants grow. In order to revegetate in soil polluted by metals, the physiological impact of the pollution on plant species should be studied in further details. As the heavy metals fluctuate in plant as well as in soil sample from site to site therefore each medicinal plant should be analyzed before utilization for pharmaceutical or traditional medicinal purposes.

REFERENCES

1. Gomez-Sagasti M. T., Alkorta I., Becerril J. M., Epelde L., Anza M. & Garbisu C. 2012. Microbial

monitoring of the recovery of soil quality during heavy metal phytoremediation. *Water Air Soil Pollut.* **223(6)**: 3249–3262.

2. Chen Y., Wang C. & Wang Z. 2005. Residues and source identification of persistent organic pollutants in farmland soils irrigated by effluents from biological treatment plants. *Environ. Int.*, **31(6)**: 778–783.
3. Al-Khazan M. M. & Al-Zlabani R. M. 2019. Toxic materials phytoremediation potential of four common trees in Saudi Arabia: A review. *Egypt. J. Exp. Biol. (Bot.)*, **15(1)**: 87-97. DOI: 10.5455/egyjeb.20190225102702.
4. Muchuweti M., Birkett J. W., Chinyanga E., Zvauya R., Scrimshaw M. D. & Lester J. N. 2006. Heavy metal content of vegetables irrigated with mixtures of wastewater and sewage sludge in Zimbabwe: implications for human health. *Agric. Ecosyst. Environ.*, **112(1)**: 41–48. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agee.2005.04.028>.
5. Erakhrumen A. A. 2007. Phytoremediation: An environmentally sound technology for pollution prevention, control and remediation in developing countries. *Educational Research and Reviews*. **2(7)**:151-156.
6. Varsha M., Nidhi M. & Anurag M. 2010. Heavy metals in plants: Phytoremediation: Plants used to remediate heavy metal pollution. *Agriculture and Biology Journal of North America*. **1(1)**: 40-46.
7. Cunningham S. D., Shann J. R., Crowley D. E. & Anderson T. A. 1997. Phytoremediation of contaminated water and soil. In: Kruger EL, Anderson TA, Coats JR, editors. *Phytoremediation of Soil and Water Contaminants*. Washington, DC: *American Chemical Society*. Ch.1: 2-17. DOI: 10.1021/bk-1997-0664.ch001.
8. Shanker A. K., Djanaguiraman M., Pathmanabhan G., Sudhagar R. & Avudainayagam S. 2003. Uptake and phytoaccumulation of chromium by selected tree species. In: *Proceedings of the international conference on water and environment* held in Bhopal, India.
9. Baker A. J., McGrath S. P., Reeves R. D. & Smith J. A. C. 2020. Metal hyper accumulator plants: A review of the ecology and physiology of a biological resource

- for phytoremediation of metal-polluted soils. *Phytoremediation of Contaminated Soil and Water*. 85. DOI: 10.1201/9780367803148
10. **Bhargava A., Carmona F. F., Bhargava M. & Srivastava S. 2012.** Approaches for enhanced phytoextraction of heavy metals. *J. Environ. Manage.* **105**: 103-120.
 11. **Nedjimi B. 2021.** Phytoremediation: a sustainable environmental technology for heavy metals decontamination. *SN Appl. Sci.* **3**. 286.
 12. **Sumiahadi A. & Acar R. 2018.** A review of phytoremediation technology: heavy metals uptake by plants. *IOP conf. Series. Earth Environ. Sci.* **142(1): 012023**.
 13. **Tangahu B. V., Sheikh S. R. A., Basri H., Idris M., Nurina A. & Muhammad M. 2011.** A review on heavy metals (As, Pb and Hg) uptake by plants through phytoremediation. *Int. J. Chem. Eng.* 1–31.
 14. **Yan A., Wang Y., Tan S. N., Mohd Yusof M. L., Ghosh S. & Chen Z. 2020.** Phytoremediation: a promising approach for revegetation of heavy metal-polluted land. *Front. Plant Sci.* **11**: 359. doi: 10.3389/fpls.2020.00359.
 15. **Mehes Smith, Melanie & Nkongolo, Kabwe & Cholewa, E. 2013.** Chapter 3: coping mechanisms of plants to metal contaminated soil. *Environmental change and sustainability*. 53-90. 10.5772/55124.
 16. **Mganga N., Manoko M. L. K. & Rulangaranga Z. K. 2011.** Classification of plants according to their heavy metal content around north mara gold mine, Tanzania: implication for phytoremediation. *Tanzan. J. Sci.* **37(1)**: 109-119. DOI:10.4314/tjs.v37i1.
 17. **Kutty A. A. & Al Mahaqeri S. A. 2016.** An Investigation of the Levels and Distribution of Selected Heavy Metals in Sediments and Plant Species within the Vicinity of Ex-Iron Mine in Bukit Besi. *J. Chem.* 1-12. DOI:10.1155/2016/2096147.
 18. **Kachenga L., Chabwela H. & Nixon M. K. 2020.** Phytoremediation potential of indigenous plants growing at Nchanga mine in Chingola, Zambia. *Open J. Ecol.* **10 (2)**: 45–61.
 19. **Mensah A. K. 2015.** “Role of revegetation in restoring fertility of degraded mined soils in Ghana: a review. *Int. J. Biodivers. Conserv.* **7 (2)**: 57–80. DOI:10.5897/IJBC2014.0775
 20. **Mganga N. D. 2014.** The potential of bioaccumulation and translocation of heavy metals in plant species growing around the tailing dam in Tanzania. *Int. J. Sci. Technol. (IJST)*. **3(10)**: 690–697.
 21. **Mkumbo S. 2012.** Development of a Low Cost Remediation Method for Heavy Metal Polluted Soil. *TRITA LWR Licentiate, Thesis*, p. 2067.
 22. **Mkumbo S., Mwegoha W. & Renman G. 2012.** Assessment of the phytoremediation potential for Pb, Zn and Cu of Indigenous plants growing in a gold mining area in Tanzania, *Int. J. Environ. Sci.* **2(4)**: 2425-2434.
 23. **Belford E. 2017.** Heavy metals accumulation by indigenous plants growing in contaminated soil in a gold mining area in Ghana. *J. Nat. Sci. Res.* **7(24)**: 40–41.
 24. **Rashed M. N. 2010.** Monitoring of contaminated toxic and heavy metals, from mine tailings through age accumulation, in soil and some wild plants at southeast Egypt. *J. Hazard Mater.* **178 (1–3)**: 739–746. DOI: 10.1016/j.jhazmat.2010.01.147.
 25. **Sadiq T. F., Samsuri A. W., Karam D. S. & Aris A. Z. 2016.** Phytoremediation of gold mine tailings amended with iron-coated and uncoated rice husk ash by vetiver grass (*Vetiveria zizanioides* L.). *Appl. Environ. Soil Sci.* 2016. DOI:10.1155/2016/4151898
 26. **Wao A. A., Khare S. & Ganguly S. 2014.** Evaluation of Phytoremediation Potential of *Datura innoxia* for Heavy Metals in an Industrially Polluted Area in Bhopal, India. *Int. J. of Futurist. Tre. In Engine. & Tech.* **2**: 16-18.
 27. **Kahangwa C. A., Nahonyo C. L., George S. B. & Eliakira K. N. 2021.** Assessing phytoremediation potentials of selected plant species in restoration of environments contaminated by heavy metals in gold mining areas of Tanzania. *Research article, Heliyon.* **7(9)**: e07979.
 28. **Panhekar D., Belkhole S., Kalambe A. & Dawle N. 2015.** Phytoremediation potential of *Lantana camara* and *Polygonum glabrum* for arsenic and nickel contaminated soil. *Res. J. Chem. Sci.*, **5(8)**: 18–22.

29. Fang J., Jia Y., Zhang C., Zhang S., Xu X., Pu Y., Li T. & Li Y. 2014. Effects of cadmium on growth response of *Lantana camara* L. and its accumulation, translocation and subcellular distribution of Cd. *Ecol. Environ. Sci.* **10**: 10–17.
30. Pandey S. K., Bhattacharya T. & Chakraborty S. 2015. Metal phytoremediation potential of naturally growing plants on fly ash dumpsite of Patratu thermal power station, Jharkhand, India. *Int. J. Phytoremed.* **18(1)**: 87–93.
31. Pandey S. K. & Bhattacharya T. 2018. Effect of two biodegradable chelates on metals uptake, translocation and biochemical changes of *Lantana camara* growing in fly ash amended soil. *Int. J. Phytoremed.* **20(3)**: 214–224.
32. Li Z., Ma Z., Kuijp Tsering Jan van der., Yuan Z. & Huang L. 2013. A review of soil heavy metal pollution from mines in China: Pollution and health risk assessment, *Science of The Total Environment*, **468–469**: 843-853.
33. Shi T., Zhang Y., Gong Y., Ma J., Wei H., Wu X., Zhao L. & Hou H. 2019. Status of cadmium accumulation in agricultural soils across China (1975–2016): From temporal and spatial variations to risk assessment, *Chemosphere*. **230**: 136-143. doi: 10.1016/j.chemosphere.2019.04.208.
34. Huang Z., Yan B., Yang Z., Wang Y., Xie R., Cen Z., Zhang L., Ding X., Awasthi M. & Chen T. 2022. Heavy metal pollution in a black shale post-mining site of southern China: Pollution pattern, source apportionment and health risk assessment, *Environ. Res.* **1**: 114950. doi: 10.1016/j.envres.2022.114950.
35. Lu Y., Song S., Wang R., Liu Z., Meng J., Sweetman A. J., Jenkins A., Ferrier R. C., Li H., Luo W. & Wang T. 2015. Impacts of soil and water pollution on food safety and health risks in China, *Environ. Int.* **77**: 5-15. doi: 10.1016/j.envint.2014.12.010.
36. Gardea-torresdey J. L., Peralta-vidua, J. De la Rosa, G. & Parsons J. G. 2005. Phytoremediation of heavy metals and study of the metal coordination by X-ray absorption spectroscopy. *Coordination Chemistry Reviews*. **249**: 1797-1810.
37. Nirola R., Megharaj M., Palanisami T., Aryal R., Venkateswarlu K. & Naidu R. 2015. Evaluation of interaction of major native trees colonizing an abandoned copper mine soil with heavy metals - a quest for phytostabilization. *J. of Sustain. Mini.* **14**: 115-123.
38. Ashraf S., Ali. Q., Zahir Z. & Hafiz A. 2019. Phytoremediation: environmentally sustainable way for reclamation of heavy metal polluted soils. *Ecotoxicology. Environ. Safe.* **174**: 714-727.

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